

FORMATION OF STUDENTS 'CREATIVE ACTIVITY ON THE BASIS OF CREDIT MODULE TECHNOLOGY

Sojida Nasridinovna Najiyeva¹

¹ Teacher of the Department of Pedagogy and Psychology

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4707329>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 15th April 2021

Accepted: 19th April 2021

Online: 21st April 2021

KEY WORDS

Community, Teacher, Coach, Education, Pupils, Students, Young People, High School, Teachers, Tasks, Skills

ABSTRACT

This article argues that the growth and development of a society depends on the abundance and potential of educated people. It is the duty of teachers and educators to educate the next generation. The carelessness and frustration of the tutor in teaching does not cause the student to become illiterate without knowledge. That the intellectual and spiritual potential of the younger generation is an important factor in the strength of our country. Students studying in high school should become professionals who have thoroughly mastered the theoretical and practical knowledge of their profession. It also talks about the role of the teacher, the role of the student and the credit-module system.

The responsibility of governing a society has largely rested with knowledgeable, enlightened people. So it is no secret to any of us that the growth and development of a society depends on the abundance and potential of educated people. Given these considerations, it is no secret to any of us that it is the task of educators to educate the next generation in an educated, knowledgeable way. The carelessness and frustration of the tutor in teaching should not lead to the ignorance of the students. The intellectual and spiritual potential of the younger generation is an important factor in the strength of our country.

Students studying in high school should become professionals who have thoroughly mastered the theoretical and practical knowledge of their profession. The task of the teacher is to equip the student with knowledge, skills and competencies. The task

of the student is to thoroughly acquire knowledge, skills and competencies. It is not necessary to invent a quality and attach it to a person - it is necessary to identify and cultivate the qualities that are present in a person. Chapters V-VI of the work of the Czech pedagogue J. Comenius "The Great Didactics" describe the essence and qualities of human nature, his ability to know the world around him. It emphasizes that a person's ability to aspire to know is innate and infinite. "The human mind embraces not only what it sees, but also past and distant norms and events, ascends to heights, and even tries to learn incredible things. Even if a person lived on earth for a thousand years, he would be constantly learning something new, learning something, and then he would be able to perceive other things." (P. 14).

The ECTS (European Credit Transfer System) system is an important part of the

education system abroad. Our higher education institutions have also moved to a credit-module system. How does this happen in a credit-module system? First of all, let's talk about the credit-module system. The credit-module system is a process of organizing education, an assessment model based on a set of modular technologies of teaching and credit measurement. Currently, professors and teachers are giving students an idea about the credit-module system. There are also problems with how to teach students in the credit-module system. Carrying it as a whole is a multifaceted and complex systemic process. The credit-module principle focuses on two main issues: ensuring the independent work of students; assessment of students' knowledge on the basis of ratings. The main tasks of the credit-module system are:

- organization of educational processes on a modular basis;
 - determining the value of one subject, course (credit);
 - assessment of students' knowledge on the basis of rating points;
 - to allow students to create their own curricula individually;
 - increase the share of independent learning in the educational process;
 - Convenience of educational programs and the possibility of change based on the demand for specialists in the labor market.
- The above is not only to teach on the basis of innovative educational technologies, but also to teach students to study independently, to take a new approach to education, to acquire the necessary and in-depth theoretical knowledge, to form practical skills based on the demands of the labor market. This means that students need to study and research independently in order to enrich their knowledge independently. In short, this system is focused on the professional development and maturity of the student. It is

aimed at ensuring the lifelong learning of the owner of knowledge and the formation of human capital that can meet the labor market and modern requirements. Let us now briefly consider the essence of the concepts of module and credit. A module is a part of a curriculum that covers several subjects and courses. It is a set of several disciplines (courses) aimed at developing students' knowledge and skills, the ability to think analytically and logically. In this case, the teacher organizes the learning process, reads live, video and audio lectures, coordinates and monitors the activities of the student. The student learns the topic independently, and realizes that he / she needs to work harder on himself / herself. According to foreign experience, the educational process in the credit-module system consists of 2-4 modules per semester. The disciplines summarized in the module are easily formed from complex to theoretical, from methodological to practical disciplines, and on the basis of the principle of logical complementarity. In order to become a specialist, a student must have the skills not only to process information, but also to process it and put it into practice.

Credit is a unit of study load (time) spent on the study and mastering of disciplines in a particular field of study or program (course). Credit is a minimum amount of time set by a normative document for a student to study in the classroom and independently, usually for a week. Credit is given to a student after completing the assignments in a particular subject and successfully passing the final exam. Each student must accumulate credits in order to receive a diploma in their chosen field and specialty in the future. Accumulated credit will continue to serve the student throughout his life to improve his skills or get additional higher education. In economic terms, the accumulated credit becomes a student's

academic "asset". Credit technology gives learners the right to choose the elective subjects included in the working curriculum, thereby directly participating in the formation of an individual curriculum. They are given the freedom to choose not only subjects but also professors. Giving students the opportunity to choose subjects is a positive thing. It is also an indicator of the specific value of evaluating learning processes. The introduction of the credit accumulation scale not only gave the student greater freedom, but also provided an opportunity to independently plan the academic process so that he or she could become a competitive professional in his or her chosen field in the future. At the same time, it has led to improvements in the assessment system and educational technologies. As stated in the Bologna Declaration, the credit-module system focuses on independent learning and serves two main functions: first, the mobility of students and teachers, the free transfer from one higher education institution to another (transfer of study or work). provides; second, the academic load - credit for all educational and research activities of the student in the chosen field of study or specialty is clearly calculated. The sum of the credits shows how much the student has mastered according to the chosen program. In doing so, the student realizes and acts on the need to work independently to score points.

It is known that we had limited access to information sources and various international databases. As a result, the main focus of professors in higher education was to search for information, assimilate it and pass the acquired information to students. That is, teachers were simply the subject of receiving and transmitting information. In this case, the student acts as a receiver of information as an object of the educational process, spending most of his time listening to lectures in the

classroom. Today, due to the acceleration of access to information, the expansion of access to international scientific and technical databases, the acceleration of globalization, the issue of developing independent education of students has been on the agenda and has become a requirement of today.

So, in the traditional system, no materials were provided on what knowledge the student will acquire in the future, what kind of professors and teachers will teach, the profile of the direction, the summary of subjects. However, all information about the direction and specialties of education in all universities of developed countries, in particular, a brief syllabus of subjects reflected in the curriculum (subject identification, information about the professor, lesson description, purpose of science, learning outcomes, teaching methods, science plans, literature, assessment methodology), professors and teachers who teach in the disciplines and their achievements, brief requirements for specialists in the labor market, ie what theoretical, practical knowledge, skills and professional qualifications are available on the official website of the university will be published. At the moment, unfortunately, applicants find it difficult to find this information on the websites of our universities. In this regard, the time has come to form a culture.

As noted above, the first steps are being taken to overcome the negative aspects of the traditional education system and to organize work within the requirements of international standards. Currently, all higher education institutions of the country are actively working on the transition to a credit-module system. All forces are being mobilized to create this system. An example of this is the fact that the El-Yurt Umidi Foundation regularly organizes seminars in foreign higher

education institutions by citizens who are engaged in research and teaching activities, and are familiar with the credit-module system.

In order to fully implement these processes, the relevant departments are being established in the higher education institution. In particular, the Tashkent State University of Economics has a department of education credit system management. This department has begun work on the full transformation of all areas of education and specialties taught at the university from the 2020/2021 academic year to the ECTS credit-module system. This does not mean that this system is fully consistent with our worldview, conditions, our values aimed at the development of a harmoniously developed person. Therefore, we need to change the views of professors and students, who are the active elements of the educational process, to absorb the requirements of this system, to form a unique culture. After all, if we do not train personnel in accordance with the requirements of the labor market, we must feel that we will inevitably lose our place in the competition. But we have no better way or choice. After all, higher education institutions in all developed countries are following this path and achieving high results. The introduction of this system is an important factor in the collaboration of teacher and student. In

modular education, the teacher organizes, directs, advises, checks the process of mastering the listener. The student, on the other hand, moves independently toward the oriented object.

Most importantly, a wide range of opportunities for students to study independently will be created. The transition to a credit-modular education system will increase the commitment and demand for university professors. With a modular learning system, the teacher performs not only informational and supervisory functions, but also advisory and coordinating functions. The leading role of the teacher in the pedagogical process is preserved. To do this, professors must increase their responsibility in the educational process, work hard on themselves, introduce a system of "teacher-student" with the broad involvement of talented students in innovative ideas created by them. The teacher should encourage each prospective professional to develop their universal competencies while being interested in their future. At the same time, students' love and confidence in their chosen profession, modern knowledge and professional competencies serve as a basis for achieving the goals set for the development of mature personnel in our country.

References:

1. Voxid Urinov PhD, Associate Professor, University of New Brunswick, Faculty of Law, Canada vokhid.urinov@unb.ca Member of the International Council of Experts under the El-Yurt Umidi Foundation August 10, 2020.
2. Ya.A. Komensky Great Didactic Teacher Publishing House-2000.
3. Sultonova G.A. Pedagogical skills. - T .: TDPU named after Nizami, 2005.